

AUTOMATION OF WASTEWATER TREATMENT PROCESS AND MONITORING THROUGH SCADA SYSTEM.

Salohiddinov Fayzulloh Fazliddin o'g'li assistant,
Andijan Mechine-building Institute
Republic of Uzbekistan, Andijan
Phone: (+998) 99 326-09-88
E-mail: salohiddinovfayzulloh60@gmail.com
ORCID: 0009-0003-3712-340X

Abstract: Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems play a crucial role in the efficient operation and management of wastewater treatment facilities. These systems integrate various technologies to monitor, control, and optimize the complex processes involved in treating wastewater. Here's an overview of the SCADA system in wastewater treatment:

Keywords: SCADA systems, wastewater treatment plant, PLC, HMI, software, hardware, license, screens, automation, communication network.

Introduction. The trend in wastewater treatment is toward more diversified and complex processes. This also leads to the need for a consistent operation, where automation is becoming increasingly important. This project includes: - Identification of each object and description of destination and function. Its automation and competence are in accordance with the specification. Application of automation in wastewater treatment operation has two primary functions: data acquisition and process control. For the former function, the level of automation is relatively high. The thousands of variables, which are gathered on-line in the SCADA systems of treatment plants, and data analysis are standard components of the treatment operation and quality monitoring. There are several indications that the situation is changing and that the treatment industry is experiencing a transition towards a higher level of automation for both information acquisition and process control. The importance of process automation at municipal wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) has increased as treatment requirements have tightened and the processes have therefore become more complicated. Since the implementation of the European Directive 91/271/CEE regarding urban wastewater treatment, environmental water protection has gained increasing public awareness among European Union Countries. The treatment requirements for the WWTPs are determined together with national legislation based on the

implementation of the European Directives, depending on the sensitivity of the receiving water body in terms of eutrophication, especially for nitrogen removal requirements. The necessity of cost-efficient and reliable treatment processes has considerably increased in order to meet the continuously more stringent level of environmental regulations and, on a larger scale, to achieve the challenging national targets for nutrient load reduction into water bodies. As a result of these regulations, major upgrading and new construction works have taken place, in particular for more efficient nutrient removal. Implementing more advanced Instrumentation, Control and Automation (ICA) system represents the right way of renovating a WWTP, leading to the more optimal use of the unit processes [1,2]. Moreover, on-line measurements and controls based on them are essential in the flexible and cost-effective operation of modern nutrient removal plants.

Materials and Methods. *General description of the chambers.* Gardabani WWTP is receiving waste water at the inlet chamber through five inlet pipelines: Main Collector 1: Tbilisi, Rustavi, Gardabani 1 Concrete Pipeline Dia. 3,300 mm Main Collector 2: Nitrogen Concrete Pipeline Dia. 1,200 mm Industrial 1: Power Plant Steel Pipeline Dia. 245 mm Industrial 2: Power Plant Steel Pipeline Dia. 245 mm Collector: Gardabani 2 Steel Pipeline Dia. 325 mm Block scheme of the wastewater treatment plant is shown in Fig. 1.

Grit Chambers. The aerated grit chamber and grease trap are the first stage of the biological process, following the principles of an adsorption-activated-sludge-process (AB-process). The grit removal and the high loaded aeration tank are one unit. The combined function is biological treatment and sand plus grease removal. Four grit and grease removal tanks will be constructed, each capable of handling 25% of the maximum flow under rainy conditions. Hydraulically even higher flows can be treated,

but efficiency will decrease. Grit will be removed in order to reduce the risk of damage to the mechanical equipment in the following treatment units, and grease will be removed to avoid nonaesthetic conditions caused by the volatile organics and malodorous floating sludge. The settled grit will be transported to the grit classifier then unloaded into a container. The retained grease will be scraped off and discharged into a grease collector shaft. Grit chambers of the wastewater treatment plant are shown in Fig. 3

Fig. 3. Grit chambers of the wastewater treatment plant.

Distribution Wells Currently two (2) distribution chambers are used to hydraulically distribute the pretreated wastewater to the primary clarifiers through weirs, equipped with shut-off gates.

Precipitation Station The ferric chloride dosing plant is a stand-alone plant which starts with a signal from the treatment works control system. The ferric chloride dosing plant has the ability to accept a signal to pace the dosing pumps in response to flow, through the WWTP Outlet channel. Storage tank for the ferric chloride is located indoors, frost free and is isolated in a separate frame to protect from accidental leakage. The ferric chloride is dosed into the two outlet shafts of the grit chambers (object 070) to the distribution chambers of the primary sedimentation tanks in proportion to their respective waste water flow rate [5,6].

Flocculant Station The polymer preparation system is designed as an automatic

preparation plant for polymer powder. The storage for the polymer powder is designed for a 10-day functioning. The polymer solution shall be dosed into the distribution wells of the primary sedimentation tanks in proportion to their respective wastewater flow rate. The flocculant station is equipped with four dosing pumps. Two redundant dosing pumps are provided for each of their dosing lines.

Primary Clarification There are ten (10) round shaped primary clarification basins in the plant of which five (5) units are currently in operation. The diameter of the units is 50 m. The primary clarifiers remove readily settleable solids and floating materials and reduce the suspended solids content. The purpose of the primary clarifiers is to remove a substantial portion of the organic solids from the untreated wastewater, with a resulting decrease in the organic and solid loadings in effluent channel. Flocculant station of the wastewater treatment plant is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Flocculant station of the wastewater treatment plant.

Treated wastewater will be discharged into outlet channel. The settled sludge on one hand will be pumped to the aerated unit chamber to activate a biological treatment process and to

treatment stage. On the other hand, primary sludge will be pumped to the static thickener. Primary clarification of the wastewater treatment plant is shown in Fig.

Fig. 5. Primary clarification of the wastewater treatment plant.

increase the efficiency of the mechanical

Outlet Channel The clarified waste water is discharged into the outlet channel. The water then enters the WWTP's original bypass channel and subsequently the runoff channel of the plant.

Sludge Machinery Station The pressured air for aerobic sludge stabilization and for A-stage is produced in the sludge machinery station. Inside the sludge machinery station three turbo blowers are installed in a separate room. The turbo blowers are designed for 6,500 Nm³/h, each with a pressure difference of 650 mbar. The air demand is calculated for a fine bubble aeration system in the stabilization tank. The blower

capacities are adequate to keep the minimum oxygen concentration in the stabilization tanks at 0.5 mg/l minimum. The blower units aerating the sludge stabilization stage are monitored through pressure, temperature and flow sensors and registered in the Process Control System (PCS) [9].

Primary Pumping Stations Raw sludge from the primary clarifiers is pumped through 2 (two) raw sludge pumping station towards the sludge drying beds. Primary pumping stations of the wastewater treatment plant is shown in Fig. 6

Fig. 6. Primary pumping stations of the wastewater treatment plant.

Sludge Drying Beds Dewatered sludge is loaded to a tractor wagon and disposed of. There are three (3) of ten (10) sludge beds in operation in the plant.

Results and Discussion. It's important to note that the actual results achieved by implementing a SCADA system can vary depending on the specific implementation, the

quality of the system deployed, and the operational practices of the wastewater treatment facility. Regular updates and continuous improvement are essential to maintaining the effectiveness of SCADA systems in the long term.

General architecture for the SCADA SYSTEM GARDABANI is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. General architecture for the SCADA SYSTEM GARDABANI.

The structure of the SCADA system, for remote dispatching, gives the service personnel of the station the following possibilities:

- monitoring the condition of equipment at a remote station (parameters of technological process, emergency and work lock conditions);
- to perform remote control of the system, without calling a specialist directly to the remote

object; - monitoring quality indicators of the water purification;

- archiving data (DBMS) on technological progress, keep an event log, view equipment crashes, and view graphs of time-adjusted parameter changes. Base system and operator interface:

- base system: operator workstation based on an PC with the SCADA system installed;

- operator interface: a set of graphical screens with a mnemonic representation of the treatment facilities structure, light indication and audible alarm [10].

Conclusion. In summary, SCADA systems in wastewater treatment contribute to the efficient and reliable operation of treatment plants by providing real-time monitoring, control capabilities, and data analysis tools, ultimately helping to ensure compliance with environmental regulations and standards. In conclusion, the integration of Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems into wastewater treatment facilities has proven to be a transformative and indispensable tool for optimizing performance, ensuring utilization and improving overall efficiency. The advantages gained from the implementation of SCADA systems highlight the importance of managing complex wastewater treatment processes.

Surveillance of water supply systems is imperative in most European countries for public health services because safe water is an important factor in preventing illness.

1) During the technological processes carried out in the Gardabani treatment plant, it

was found that, following the measurements, a negative impact on the environment is presented by the following pollutants: CBO5, ammoniac nitrogen, sulphides and hydrogen sulphide, chlorides.

2) Following the monitoring of the station, it was found that these pollutants fall within the limits prescribed by the legislation, having a minor impact on the environment.

3) After the automation, each object in the station works with 20% higher efficiency compared to the old nonautomated system.

4) Every second, the data from all the sensors in the station is saved. Based on this data, automated reports are generated by operators at the desired time, with their help, the power station's efficiency and water quality can be seen.

5) After automation of the station for 25 years there will only be expenditures for energy and personnel, that is a 30- 40% reduction of expenses compared to the non-automated station.

6) Remote control via SCADA makes the station more flexible to monitor and control.

7) The working precision of all automation equipment has increased by 2 times, this increases their unmanaged operating term.

REFERENCES

1. Azamat, Y., & Fayzulloh, S. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF A WIRELESS WATER QUALITY MONITORING SYSTEM FOR WATER TREATMENT FACILITIES. *Unversum: технические науки*, (5-10 (98)), 23-26.
Url: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/development-of-a-wireless-water-quality-monitoring-system-for-water-treatment-facilities>
2. ALIJONOVICH, Y. A. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF A WIRELESS WATER QUALITY MONITORING SYSTEM FOR WATER TREATMENT FACILITIES. *Unversum: технические науки*.
Url: <https://scienceweb.uz/publication/11271>
3. ALIJONOVICH, Y. A. (2022). DESIGN OF WIRELESS WATER QUALITY MONITORING SYSTEM FOR WATER TREATMENT FACILITIES. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*.
Url: <https://scienceweb.uz/publication/11262>
4. Fazliddin o'g'li, S. F. (2023). IOT (INTERNET OF THINGS) GA ASOSLANGAN OQAVA VA CHIQUINDI SUVLARI SIFATI MONITORINGI TIZIMINI LOYIHALASH. *Mexatronika va robototexnika: muammolar va rivojlantirish istiqbollari*, 1(1), 414-417.
Url: <https://michascience.com/index.php/mrmri/article/view/140>

5. Fayzulloh, S., & Salohiddin, G. U. (2023). REAKTIV QUUVVAT NAZORATINI BOSHQARISH JARAYONINI MATLAB DASTURIDA MODELLASHTIRISH. FAN, JAMIYAT VA INNOVATSIYALAR, 1(1), 147-153.
Url: <https://michascience.com/index.php/fji/article/view/26>
6. Fayzulloh, S., & Islombek, S. (2023). THE USE OF RADAR SENSORS IN MEASURING SATURATION. FAN, JAMIYAT VA INNOVATSIYALAR, 1(1), 126-131.
Url: <https://michascience.com/index.php/fji/article/view/23>
7. Fayzulloh, S., & Sanjarbek, A. (2023). REACTIVE POWER COMPENSATION: ENHANCING POWER SYSTEM EFFICIENCY AND STABILITY. FAN, JAMIYAT VA INNOVATSIYALAR, 1(1), 132-137.
Url: <https://michascience.com/index.php/fji/article/view/24>
8. Azamat, Y., & Fayzulloh, S. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF A WIRELESS WATER QUALITY MONITORING SYSTEM FOR WATER TREATMENT FACILITIES. Universum: технические науки, (5-10 (98)), 23-26.
Url: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/development-of-a-wireless-water-quality-monitoring-system-for-water-treatment-facilities>
9. ALIJONOVICH, Y. A. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF A WIRELESS WATER QUALITY MONITORING SYSTEM FOR WATER TREATMENT FACILITIES. Unversum: технические науки.
Url: <https://scienceweb.uz/publication/11271>
10. ALIJONOVICH, Y. A. (2022). DESIGN OF WIRELESS WATER QUALITY MONITORING SYSTEM FOR WATER TREATMENT FACILITIES. EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD).
Url: <https://scienceweb.uz/publication/11262>
11. Fazliddin o'g'li, S. F. (2023). IOT (INTERNET OF THINGS) GA ASOSLANGAN OQAVA VA CHIQUINDI SUVLARI SIFATI MONITORINGI TIZIMINI LOYIHALASH. Mexatronika va robototexnika: muammolar va rivojlantirish istiqbollari, 1(1), 414-417.
Url: <https://michascience.com/index.php/mrmri/article/view/140>
12. Fayzulloh, S., & Salohiddin, G. U. (2023). REAKTIV QUUVVAT NAZORATINI BOSHQARISH JARAYONINI MATLAB DASTURIDA MODELLASHTIRISH. FAN, JAMIYAT VA INNOVATSIYALAR, 1(1), 147-153.
Url: <https://michascience.com/index.php/fji/article/view/26>
13. Fayzulloh, S., & Islombek, S. (2023). THE USE OF RADAR SENSORS IN MEASURING SATURATION. FAN, JAMIYAT VA INNOVATSIYALAR, 1(1), 126-131.
Url: <https://michascience.com/index.php/fji/article/view/23>
14. Fayzulloh, S., & Sanjarbek, A. (2023). REACTIVE POWER COMPENSATION: ENHANCING POWER SYSTEM EFFICIENCY AND STABILITY. FAN, JAMIYAT VA INNOVATSIYALAR, 1(1), 132-137.
Url: <https://michascience.com/index.php/fji/article/view/24>